

The Future of Historical Heritage Management: When Blockchain meets Art

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Abstract— This paper explores the integration of blockchain and related technologies for enhancing cultural heritage management systems. Art counterfeiting and inefficiencies in traditional provenance methods highlight the need for robust solutions to ensure the security, authenticity, and traceability of artifacts. Blockchain’s immutability, transparency, and decentralized structure provide an innovative foundation for addressing these challenges. By incorporating tools such as invisible marking technologies, AI-driven authentication, and user-friendly decentralized applications (DAPPs), this framework enables efficient management of artifact records and ownership. Additionally, the application of Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) and Blockchain as a Service (BaaS) platforms demonstrates how scalable and secure systems can be deployed to meet the growing demands of the art world. The proposed methodology also considers interdisciplinary approaches involving chemistry, AI, and blockchain technologies to safeguard cultural artifacts while enhancing stakeholder trust and operational efficiency.

Index Terms—cultural heritage, art, blockchain, AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE authenticity and history of artworks are crucial for maintaining their economic value and protecting their historical and cultural importance. Art counterfeiting weakens these foundations, presenting an ongoing challenge in the art market by reducing the value of genuine works and disrupting normal market operations. This issue leads to significant financial losses and damages trust among collectors, dealers, and institutions.

Well-known cases highlight the weaknesses in traditional methods of verifying artworks. For example, the Knoedler Gallery scandal involved the sale of approximately \$80 million worth of fake paintings falsely presented as newly discovered works by famous artists like Mark Rothko and Jackson Pollock [1]. The gallery relied on forged documents about the artworks' history and expert opinions without thorough scientific analysis, revealing the shortcomings of conventional authentication processes.

Similarly, Wolfgang Beltracchi created extensive forgeries by producing paintings wrongly attributed to early 20th-century artists like Heinrich Campendonk and Max Ernst [2]. Beltracchi's advanced techniques, which included using materials appropriate for the period and mimicking historical styles, deceived art experts and collectors for years. His case underscores the need for better methods to detect forgeries that

can bypass traditional expert evaluation.

The Greenhalgh family conducted a 17-year operation creating and selling fake ancient and modern artworks, including a supposed Egyptian statue and a counterfeit sculpture attributed to Paul Gauguin [3]. Their forgeries entered respected institutions and markets, further demonstrating art fraud's varied and sophisticated nature. Additionally, incidents like the 2002 theft of masterpieces from the Van Gogh Museum emphasize the challenges in securing and verifying artworks, highlighting the need for strong systems to maintain the honesty of art transactions.

Traditional methods of tracking an artwork's history, which depend heavily on expert evaluations and historical records, are often insufficient due to incomplete documentation and vulnerability to manipulation. Documents can be forged, and expert opinions may vary or be influenced, leading to doubts in authentication. These limitations create a situation where fake artworks can circulate undetected, weakening confidence in the art market.

The rapid growth of blockchain technology offers a promising solution to these challenges by providing a decentralized and secure way to track the ownership and history of art objects. Blockchain is a distributed ledger technology that allows safe, transparent, and unchangeable recording of transactions across multiple computers in a network [4]. Each transaction is validated through agreement among the participants, ensuring no single party can alter the data independently.

In the art world, blockchain can be used to create permanent records of an artwork's history, documenting its creation, sales history, and ownership transfers in a transparent yet secure way from unauthorized changes. By recording each transaction on the blockchain, stakeholders can trace the complete history of an artwork, building trust and reducing the risk of fraud.

However, adopting blockchain in cultural heritage management faces several challenges. One main concern is the "garbage in, garbage out" problem: the accuracy of the blockchain record entirely depends on the correctness of the data entered. If a fake artwork is initially registered on the blockchain as genuine, the unchangeable nature of the ledger means this false information becomes permanently recorded and widely spread as truth. Therefore, there is a critical need for reliable authentication before an artwork is entered into the blockchain system. This requires the involvement of trusted

authorities or the development of automated systems capable of verifying authenticity accurately.

Another challenge is the technological complexity and associated costs for those involved, such as galleries, auction houses, and artists. Many may lack the technical expertise or financial resources to implement and maintain blockchain systems effectively. Integrating blockchain technology involves initial setup costs and ongoing maintenance, security measures, and training for staff to manage and use the system properly.

Moreover, differences in government regulations across different countries present obstacles to the widespread adoption of blockchain solutions in the art market. Legal frameworks concerning digital transactions, data privacy, and protection of cultural heritage vary internationally, potentially leading to compliance issues. A globally adopted policy or set of standards would be necessary to address these differences and facilitate the smooth implementation of blockchain technology for tracking art history and preventing counterfeiting.

To address above-mentioned constraints, in this paper, we present our vision of cultural heritage preservation and protection by robust and cost-effective blockchain-based methodology for tracking and proving the authenticity of artworks in a user-friendly manner for stakeholders operating in the field. The main contributions of this paper are the following:

1. We present an overview of the existing blockchain-based solutions for tracking art objects.
2. We propose a novel interdisciplinary methodology for robust and cost-effective management of art objects leveraging chemistry, AI, and blockchain technologies.
3. We deeply analyze the state-of-the-art blockchain implementations and their suitability for art provenance and management.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II outlines the state-of-the-art blockchain-based solutions for art cultural heritage management. Section III describes the proposed methodology based on blockchain and AI. Section IV analyses existing blockchain implementations and discusses their suitability for the proposed framework. Section V concludes the paper.

II. BLOCKCHAIN-BASED HERITAGE MANAGEMENT

A. Key Features of the Blockchain Technology for the Heritage Management

Blockchain is a distributed ledger technology that offers a scalable and decentralized platform for storing, verifying, and validating transactions between different parties. This system establishes trust among participants without needing a central authority or intermediary [5-8]. The most prominent example of blockchain technology is Bitcoin, the first cryptocurrency, where the distributed ledger records the entire transaction history of all registered wallets and is maintained collectively by all nodes in the network [9].

The term "blockchain" reflects its structural design—a chain of blocks linked together to enforce a strict chronological order.

Each block contains a set of transactions recorded during a specific timeframe. After the transactions are compiled, a cryptographic hash function is applied to the entire block's data, producing a unique hash value that serves as a digital fingerprint for that block. This hash value is then included in the header of the subsequent block, effectively linking the two blocks together.

This chaining mechanism ensures the integrity and immutability of the blockchain. If an attempt is made to alter any past transaction within a block, the hash value of that block would change, leading to a mismatch with the hash stored in the following block. This inconsistency would propagate through all subsequent blocks, immediately signaling tampering to the network. Since the blockchain is distributed across many nodes, all holding copies of the ledger, it becomes practically impossible for a malicious actor to alter historical data without gaining control over most of the network's computing power.

Figure 1 illustrates this principle, highlighting how each block's hash value links it to the next, forming an unbreakable chain. This design ensures that the data within the blockchain remains secure and transparent, allowing participants to trust the validity of transactions without relying on a centralized third party. The consensus mechanisms employed by blockchain networks further reinforce this trust by requiring network-wide agreement for any new transactions or alterations, thereby safeguarding the system against fraud and unauthorized modifications.

Fig. 1. The example of transaction validation in blockchain.

Each transaction associated with a piece of art is stored as a block, and these blocks are chained together in chronological order, forming a secure and permanent record. This digital ledger ensures that any future buyer or evaluator can verify an artwork's authenticity by reviewing its entire documented history, thereby reducing the risk of acquiring a counterfeit piece. Moreover, blockchain allows artists to register their works at the point of creation, creating a digital certificate of authenticity permanently linked to the artwork. This digital certificate can be transferred whenever the piece changes hands, ensuring the artwork's provenance remains intact. While blockchain alone cannot prevent forgers from creating physical replicas, it can provide buyers, galleries, and auction houses with a robust tool to verify the legitimacy of a piece, reducing fraud and increasing trust in the art market due to several key features explained below [10].

Immutability and Data Integrity. Blockchain is designed so that it does not allow any confirmed transaction to be altered or deleted without consensus from the network participants. This

feature ensures that records of heritage artifacts, including their provenance, historical significance, and ownership, remain tamper-proof. Such integrity is crucial for maintaining accurate historical records and preventing fraudulent claims or alterations.

Provenance and Traceability. Blockchain can chronologically record every transaction and transfer of an asset. This feature provides a transparent and verifiable history of cultural artifacts, which is essential for authenticating items, tracking their movement, and mitigating illegal traffic. This allows museums and collectors to verify the legitimacy of artifacts in case of counterfeiting, theft or regular sale.

Decentralization. Blockchain operates on a distributed network of nodes, without any central authority. Consequently, with a sufficiently large number of nodes the blockchain can eliminate the risk of data loss or manipulation, because there is no single point of failure. Decentralization ensures that heritage data is resilient against cyber-attacks and technical problems.

Tokenization of Assets. Blockchain allows to represent real-world assets as non-fungible tokens (NFTs) and store them. NFTs can be used to democratize and improve trading of art objects through public online marketplaces such as OpenSea or others. Since each NFT is unique, it can be linked to the specific art object (e.g. painting) and this link will be permanent in the blockchain. Another important feature of NFT is the traceability of history and known origin from the primary author or legitimate owner (i.e. museum, gallery, church, etc.). Thus, any further sale of the art object can be tracked by the NFT, and it becomes impossible to sell a counterfeited object because deceivers will not be able to provide a correct NFT along with the art item.

Security. Each block of transactions has a unique cryptographic hash that ensures the integrity and correctness of information. The hash is computed based on the transaction data and the hash of the previous block, so its value depends on the entire previous chain. This feature protects data from modification, as changing any transaction in the past will change the cryptographic hash value, leading to the rejection of such a block by other nodes.

Smart Contracts. This feature allows the development of any software algorithm for multiple related transactions that can be automatically executed according to defined conditions. Smart contracts can enhance the efficiency of heritage management and flexible automated agreements between museums, private collectors and governments.

B. Existing Blockchain-Based Solutions for the Art Management

One of the early adopters of blockchain in the art world is Ascribe service, founded in 2014. Ascribe is a service that allows authors to register and track their intellectual property. A unique cryptographic ID is generated and stored in the blockchain when work is registered for the first time, thus creating a permanent and unbreakable link between the creators and their work. This solution ensures that authenticity and ownership history are accurately maintained [11].

Another platform - Verisart, provides real-time certification and verification of artworks using blockchain, creating digital certificates of authenticity stored on the blockchain. These

certificates are accessible and verifiable by buyers, sellers, and auction houses, providing a reliable method for proving an artwork's authenticity and provenance [12].

Another notable platform, Artory, offers a blockchain-based registry for art and collectibles. Artory records provenance, exhibition history, and condition reports on the blockchain, ensuring that all information related to an artwork is transparent and immutable. Artory collaborates with auction houses and galleries to integrate its blockchain solution into their operations, enhancing trust and transparency in the art market [13].

Tracking the location and condition of artworks is crucial for museums, galleries, and collectors. Blockchain technology streamlines inventory management by providing a unified and secure platform for tracking artworks throughout their lifecycle. Codex Protocol serves as a decentralized title registry for art and collectibles, enabling the creation of a comprehensive and immutable record of an artwork's history, including ownership, provenance, and condition. By using blockchain, Codex ensures that this information is secure and accessible to all stakeholders, reducing fraud risk and enhancing transparency in the art market [14].

Arteia combines blockchain with RFID technology to track the movement and condition of artworks. Each artwork is equipped with an RFID tag linked to a blockchain record, providing real-time tracking and historical data. This integration enhances security and efficiency in inventory management, making it easier for museums and galleries to monitor their collections [15].

Blockchain technology also facilitates secure and transparent transactions in the art market by providing a decentralized platform for buying and selling artworks. Smart contracts can automate various aspects of art transactions, ensuring compliance with agreements and reducing the need for intermediaries [16].

Maecenas, for instance, is a blockchain-based art investment platform that allows users to buy fractional ownership in artworks. By tokenizing artworks, Maecenas enables a broader range of investors to participate in the art market. Smart contracts manage transactions and ownership transfers, ensuring transparency and reducing fraud risk [17].

Another innovative platform, DADA Art Collective, uses blockchain to create a digital marketplace for artists and collectors. Artists can tokenize their works and sell them directly to collectors, receiving royalties for future sales through smart contracts. This platform empowers artists by providing them with more control over their works and ensuring fair compensation [18].

III. BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FRAMEWORK FOR THE CULTURAL HERITAGE MANAGEMENT

A. Invisible and Unique Marking of Art Objects

To cope with art counterfeiting, researchers so far have explored various innovative methods for marking artworks in a way that is both invisible to the naked eye and nearly impossible to replicate. Thus, a key focus is mostly related to the

development of invisible markers that can be easily integrated into art objects without noticeable change of their appearance. One promising solution is to use nanoparticles or quantum dots, which are undetectable under normal viewing conditions, but can be identified with the specific lighting or specialized equipment. These nanoparticles reveal their presence only after being exposed to some predefined conditions such as electromagnetic waves [19]. Another similar solution is to use spectral markers, which are visible only under specific wavelengths such as ultraviolet or infrared light. Such methods ensure a layer of security that can be accessed when authenticity verification is needed [20]. A more sophisticated approach is to use micro-tagants embedded within the materials used in the artwork. Due to a very small size they can't be seen without magnification, so that they do not affect the visual integrity of the art piece. However, after appropriate magnification and scanning with appropriate equipment, we can extract unique numerical code of each piece of art [21].

Another challenge is to make markers both easy to verify, but difficult to repeat. Ensuring that these markers are unrepeatable is crucial to their effectiveness in preventing counterfeiting. One strategy involves the randomized generation of markers using cryptographic algorithms. These algorithms produce random, unique markers that cannot be predicted or replicated, adding a layer of mathematical security to the physical marker [22]. Each artwork can thus be assigned a one-time use code, a unique identifier that is applied only once and cannot be duplicated, making it impossible for counterfeiters to replicate the marker even if they are aware of its existence. Moreover, we need to find non-intrusive methods of marking that do not alter the artwork's appearance, composition, or longevity. This is very important for the historical and cultural value of art objects. Techniques must be carefully selected and applied to ensure they are compatible with the materials and methods used by the artist [23].

One promising concept is the use of physical unclonable functions (PUFs) [24]. A PUF can be any physical object that, for a given external influence, provides a physically defined "digital fingerprint" that can be used as a unique identifier. Due to the randomness of physical materials, PUF allows to create markers that are impossible to replicate. For example, some historical items, like paintings or sculptures have specific chemical and physical structure, which was common at the specific periods of the past, and cannot be replicated now due to the significant difference in the technical process and absent or lost documentation. Thus, a specific grain patterns of a canvas or the unique distribution of particles within the paint can be used as a natural, and unclonable marker. Such markers can be defined by using modern scanning tools, such as XRF or laser irradiation [25]. Finally, in case when physical markers are necessary, reversible markers or markers, which disappear in time are the best choice. This allows markers to be removed or deactivated without harming the artwork. Such functionality will be needed in case of future changes of ownership or authentication technology [26].

In the context of the current paper, we do not dive deep into the specific marking technology, but rather assume that all

heritage items already have a unique digital fingerprint, which can be both stored in the blockchain and scanned by the target hardware and software tools.

B. User-Friendly and Convenient Tools for Scanning the Art Objects

Scanning tools should be able to read physical or chemical markers on different art objects, such as paintings, sculptures, books, coins, etc. One of the most used tools for non-destructive art provenance spectroscopic and imaging devices. X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) spectrometers, for instance, are commonly used to determine the unique elemental composition of artworks. For example, Bruker ARTAX mobile XRF system enable on-site analysis of paintings, sculptures, coins, and manuscripts directly in museums or galleries [27]. XRF allows to identify pigments and metals in non-intrusive way, so that there is no risk of damaging the precious piece of art.

Alternative solution is Infrared Reflectography (IRR), which can capture underdrawings beneath the visible surface of paintings and reveal details that are invisible to the naked eye. For example, Osiris and Apollo IRR cameras provide high-resolution infrared imaging, which have been developed and tested on the real art objects in collaboration with the London National Gallery [28].

One more interesting approach is the Raman spectroscopy, which can identify molecular structure of materials, which can be useful to for identifying pigments or inks in paintings, manuscripts, and textiles. For example, Renishaw InVia Raman microscope provides detailed analysis of microscopic samples, that allows conservators to understand structure of materials used by artists in any original art object [29].

Further improvement can be found by multispectral and hyperspectral imaging. By capturing art objects across multiple wavelengths, we can detect more hidden details to understand history and authenticity of art objects. SPECIM IQ hyperspectral camera and Headwall Photonics Hyperspec camera are good examples of portable tools for the analysis of artworks and archeological objects [30].

Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) provides cross-sectional images of thin layers within an artwork. Systems like the Thorlabs Telesto series OCT are used for non-invasive depth profiling, examining varnish layers and subsurface features in paintings and works on paper. This technology helps conservators assess the condition of an artwork and make informed decisions about restoration efforts [31].

Conventional electronic microscopes and surface analysis tools can be also useful for an art examination. Such devices can offer high-magnification imaging of the surface, which can reveal hidden structures and properties, which are unique and cannot be counterfeited by the third parties [32].

Additional challenge is the scanning of 3D dimensional objects, such as sculptures and other artefacts. This can be achieved by the structured light scanners and laser scanners, which can capture precise 3D models using projected light patterns. These precise patterns can be used for documentation, preservation and anticounterfeiting of art objects [33].

Apart of the advanced imaging tools, additional

improvement can be achieved by implementation of the state-of-the-art AI algorithms for the further processing of the images. The most common applications are convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which can be trained to recognize unique patterns and features in artworks. AI algorithms can interpret spectral data that allows to identify pigments and inks in paintings or manuscripts, as well as recognize specific patterns for material identification [34].

In addition, AI can be used for pattern recognition within three-dimensional models. Volumetric AI analysis in 3D scans of sculptures, coins or other objects can be used to compare each item with known model in the blockchain [35]. This allows to detect even minor differences, which can be missed by humans and decrease a probability of missing the counterfeited objects. Moreover, AI can assist in conservation of sculptures by combining 3D scanning and pattern recognition for monitoring of structural changes over time [36].

C. System Model of the Blockchain-based Art Management System

First, we consider the invisible and unique marking of art objects, particularly through the use of PUFs. A PUF is a physical entity embodied in a physical structure, which is easy to evaluate but hard to predict, clone, or reproduce. Let each art object be represented by A_i , where i indexes the objects. Each art object A_i possesses a unique physical characteristic that can be measured and used as a fingerprint. We define a fingerprint extraction function:

$$F_i = \text{Extract}(A_i, \theta) \quad (1)$$

where F_i is the unique digital fingerprint of art object A_i , $\text{Extract}(\square)$ is the function that extracts the fingerprint using predefined scanning tools, and θ represents the parameters or settings of the scanning tool, such as wavelength or magnification. The property of uniqueness is crucial here; for any two different art objects A_i and A_j , where $i \neq j$, the probability that their fingerprints are identical should be approximately zero:

$$\Pr(F_i = F_j) \approx 0 \quad (2)$$

Additionally, the extraction function must be non-intrusive, ensuring that A_i remains unchanged after extraction.

Next, we model the user-friendly tools for scanning art objects as measurement functions. Scanning tools s can be represented as functions that map physical characteristics to digital data:

$$D_i = s(A_i, \theta) \quad (3)$$

where D_i is the raw data obtained from scanning A_i , and s is the scanning function, such as XRF spectroscopy or IRR imaging. The fingerprint is then generated by processing this raw data:

$$F_i = \phi(D_i)$$

where ϕ is the processing function that converts raw data D_i into a fingerprint F_i . The scanning tools must be easy to use, denoted by minimal complexity C :

$$C(s) \leq C_{\max}$$

and they must be compatible with various art objects, ensuring that for all A_i , there exists a scanning function s such that:

$$D_i = s(A_i, \theta).$$

Integrating with blockchain technology, we model the blockchain as a secure ledger. Each block B_k contains a set of transactions $T_{k,n}$, and each transaction records an event related to an art object. Smart contracts C automate processes like registration, transfer, and verification.

The blockchain storage function updates the ledger B by adding new blocks:

$$B = B \cup \{B_k\}$$

Each transaction $T_{k,n}$ includes the fingerprint hash h_i , a timestamp t_i , the owner ID O_i , and a digital signature σ_i . We use a secure hash function H to protect the fingerprint F_i :

$$h_i = H(F_i)$$

The digital signature σ_i is generated using the private key k_{O_i} of the owner O_i :

$$\sigma_i = \text{Sign}_{k_{O_i}}(h_i, t_i)$$

Smart contracts provide functions for registration, transfer, and verification. The registration function validates and records the fingerprint hash and owner:

$$\text{Register}(h_i, O_i, \sigma_i)$$

The transfer function transfers ownership from O_i to O_j :

$$\text{Transfer}(h_i, O_i, O_j, \sigma_i)$$

The verification function checks if the scanned fingerprint F_r matches the stored hash:

$$\text{Verify}(F_r) = \begin{cases} \text{True}, & \text{if } H(F_r) = h_i \\ \text{False}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The verification process depends on the selected blockchain network and consensus algorithm, which will be covered in upcoming section.

D. Choosing the Blockchain Network

Blockchain technology is a peer-to-peer system where nodes communicate directly without the need for a central authority. For managing cultural heritage, a system must ensure *immutability*, *transparency*, *security*, and the ability to handle multiple stakeholders with different levels of access and authority. A cultural heritage blockchain system should provide strong security to protect sensitive information about artifacts, such as their origin, ownership history, and condition reports. This security helps prevent unauthorized access or tampering with records, which could result in cultural and financial losses. At the same time, the system should allow authorized users to verify the authenticity and history of artifacts without exposing sensitive details.

A key component of any blockchain network is its consensus algorithm, which defines how distributed nodes validate transactions securely. Transactions are records of changes in the distributed ledger, and they must be verified by multiple nodes.

For a transaction to be secure and unchangeable, more than 51% of the nodes must agree to update the ledger with the new information [37].

The consensus algorithm determines how data is shared among blockchain nodes, how decisions are made, and how new blocks of verified transactions are added to the blockchain. While a detailed review of all consensus algorithms is beyond the scope of this paper, there are some existing works, which provide in-depth discussions on consensus algorithms [38-40]. In this paper, we focus only on the most common consensus algorithms and investigate their suitability for managing cultural heritage.

Proof-of-Work (PoW) is the first and most well-known consensus algorithm, famously implemented in the Bitcoin blockchain [4]. The core idea of PoW is a complex cryptographic puzzle, or hash, which requires significant time and energy to solve. This procedure is widely known as mining. The workflow of the mining process in PoW is following.

Let N denote the total number of nodes, H the total network hash rate, and h_i the hash rate of node i . The probability P_i of node i solving the puzzle is proportional to its hash rate, expressed as

$$P_i = \frac{h_i}{H},$$

where:

$$H = \sum_{j=1}^N h_j.$$

The average time to mine a block, is then defined as

$$T = \frac{D}{H},$$

where D is the complexity of the puzzle. To ensure security against a 51% attack, the hash rate of the arbitrary malicious actor must satisfy the following condition

$$\frac{h_{adv}}{H} < 0.5.$$

Additional level of security is achieved by including the hash of the of each block into the next block. This feature in combination with PoW consensus makes it nearly impossible for an attacker to leverage enough computing power for inserting fake transaction and verify it in time. However, despite its high level of security and decentralization, PoW has very low transaction throughput and high energy consumption, which do not allow to scale properly for worldwide heritage management system [1].

Proof-of-Stake (PoS) has emerged as a more energy-efficient alternative to PoW. Instead of relying on computational power, PoS validators are selected based on their financial stakes in the network. This process eliminates the need for intensive computations, as the validator with the largest stake is more likely to add the next block.

Let N represent the number of validators, S the total amount staked, and s_i the stake of validator i . The probability P_i of validator i being chosen is

$$P_i = \frac{s_i}{S},$$

where

$$S = \sum_{j=1}^N s_j.$$

Validators earn rewards based on their probability of selection, with the reward R_i for validator i calculated as

$$R_i = \frac{s_i}{S} \cdot R,$$

where R is the total reward.

Although this could theoretically allow wealthy users to control the network by staking 51% of the total funds, such an attack is risky and impractical due to the potential loss of staked funds. Malicious behavior results in a penalty proportional to the staked amount, expressed as $\alpha \cdot s_i$, where α is the slashing factor. In order to minimize risks of 51% attack, any stake in the network must satisfy the following condition:

$$\frac{s_{adv}}{S} < \frac{1}{3}.$$

Such limitation allows to maintain the integrity of the blockchain network. Additionally, PoS enhances security by randomly selecting validators from a pool of eligible nodes, making it unlikely for an attacker to control the majority of the network. These features allow PoS to increase the transaction throughput, decrease latency, and ensure scalability through sharding, which makes it suitable for museums and large number of heritage items. The most popular PoS blockchains include Ethereum 2.0, Polkadot, and Cosmos [41-43].

Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT) [44] employs a voting-based approach to achieve consensus, tolerating up to f Byzantine (malicious) nodes in a system which can be represented as:

$$N = 3f + 1,$$

where N is the number of nodes. Fault tolerance in PBFT is characterized by the relation:

$$f = \lfloor (N - 1) / 3 \rfloor,$$

where f represents the maximum number of faulty nodes. PBFT involves multiple rounds of communication, and the message complexity per round is:

$$m = N \cdot (N - 1),$$

accounting for each node broadcasting to all other nodes.

The time to reach consensus spans over three phases – pre prepare, prepare, and commit, resulting in a total time:

$$T = 3 \cdot t,$$

where t is the duration of one communication round.

The PBFT system remains secure as long as the number of honest nodes H satisfies the following condition:

$$H = N - f \geq 2f + 1,$$

ensuring that honest nodes dominate the consensus process [1].

Each consensus algorithm offers specific advantages and trade-offs regarding security, scalability, and efficiency. A cultural heritage management system requires high security, scalability, and efficiency levels to ensure smooth operations and prevent delays or excessive costs.

PoW is a strong choice for security, mainly due to its resistance to 51% attacks. However, its high energy and

computational demands make it less suitable for cultural heritage management, where sustainability and cost-effectiveness are essential. The cultural sector often operates with limited resources, and PoW's energy-intensive nature could conflict with the need to preserve heritage sustainably.

PoS provides an energy-efficient alternative by using economic incentives rather than computational power. For cultural heritage systems, PoS can enable secure and transparent validation of transactions, such as artifact registration or ownership transfers, while keeping costs low. However, the effectiveness of PoS relies on fair distribution of stakes, which is critical to avoid centralization and ensure trust among participants.

PBFT aligns well with the requirements of cultural heritage management, particularly for processes that need quick and reliable decisions, such as verifying artifact provenance during sales or approving loans. PBFT achieves fast consensus with deterministic finality, making it well-suited for such tasks. However, its message-intensive nature may limit scalability when the network includes many participants, such as museums and galleries.

Both PoS and PBFT are suitable options for cultural heritage systems. PoS is better for networks requiring energy efficiency and scalability, while PBFT works well in smaller, controlled environments where quick and reliable decision-making is essential. The choice of algorithm depends on the system's size, available resources, and specific use cases.

Furthermore, multi-blockchain system can combine the advantages of PoW, PoS, and PBFT to address the diverse needs of cultural heritage management [45]. A PoW layer can be used for tasks that require the highest security, such as anchoring immutable records of artifact provenance. A PoS layer can handle routine operations, such as artifact registration, ownership transfers, or condition updates, providing scalability and cost efficiency. Finally, a PBFT layer can manage real-time collaborative decisions, such as approving loans or restoration plans, where its speed and reliability are valuable. By integrating multiple blockchains into a single system, a multi-blockchain approach allows cultural heritage networks to take advantage of the strengths of each consensus algorithm while minimizing their weaknesses. This ensures a balanced, secure, and efficient framework for preserving and managing cultural heritage.

E. Practical Deployment of the Decentralized Heritage Management System Application

A system for managing historical heritage can be implemented through decentralized applications (DAPP) [46]. Developing a DAPP involves building a system where users can interact directly with the blockchain (e.g., connecting heritage site managers and visitors). A DAPP typically includes three parts: the frontend, i.e. user interface, the backend with application workflow, and smart contracts. For the heritage management system, a web or mobile app is typical choice, because it is already commonly used by museums and galleries. The frontend can be connected to the blockchain using libraries

like Web3.js or ethers.js, to enable users to perform tasks such as assets registration or verification of records. The backend handles data processing, user authentication, and access control. The backend also ensures user requests are securely transmitted to the blockchain and processed correctly.

The core part of each DAPP are the smart contracts, which are small programs written in languages like Solidity (for Ethereum). These contracts define and enforce the system's rules, such as recording ownership transfers or verifying authenticity. Technically, smart contract is a software code, which implements the logic of the transactions and conditions of their execution [47]. Once written, the smart contracts are tested using tools like Truffle or Hardhat to ensure they are secure and functional.

After testing, the smart contracts are deployed to the blockchain network, and the frontend and backend are hosted on servers or cloud platforms. Tools like IPFS (InterPlanetary File System) can securely store additional data, such as metadata or large files, while keeping the blockchain focused only on essential information [48].

A transaction is created without specifying a recipient address when deploying a smart contract. This transaction includes byte-code as input data, which acts as a constructor. The constructor is responsible for making initial changes to the storage before the contract begins execution. During deployment, the initialization byte-code is executed only once to set up the contract. In contrast, the execution byte-code is triggered each time the smart contract is subsequently invoked (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. The workflow of smart-contract deployment in blockchain.

Decentralized applications generally have their own set of related applications they use to encode business logic. They divide the execution logic between the blockchain and the user's device, as decentralized execution is resource-intensive. Primarily, the blockchain acts as a "server" that stores information about the overall state of the decentralized system [165]. All data and backend code of DAPP are decentralized and stored in blockchain, which makes them immutable and protected from external modifications. To ensure high performance and system throughput, the application architecture is implemented in such a way that the main load is handled by a centralized server (data center), while critical data is stored asynchronously in the blockchain (Figure 3) [49,50].

Fig. 3. The client-server-blockchain workflow for cultural heritage DAPP

IV. DEVELOPMENT PERSPECTIVE OF BLOCKCHAIN-BASED CULTURAL HERITAGE SYSTEMS

A. Non-Fungible Tokens in the Heritage Management Systems

Beyond enhancing security and fostering decentralized trust among multiple agents, blockchain technology offers a powerful tool for management and accounting of unique heritage items. A notable development in this area is the ERC Ethereum Request for Comments) - 721 Non-Fungible Token (NFT) Standard [51]. Unlike traditional cryptocurrencies, NFTs are characterized by their uniqueness, ensuring that each NFT is distinct from others. This feature enables the digital representation of unique real-world assets on the blockchain, facilitating their seamless transfer over the internet. Consequently, NFTs unlock a vast array of use cases through various smart contracts.

The blockchain industry has already seen significant adoption of NFTs, particularly in the development of metaverse solutions [47]. NFTs are widely used in the gaming and entertainment sectors, where they replicate virtual assets in games and metaverses. However, NFTs hold great potential beyond these areas, especially within the context of contemporary and historical art objects, by providing a secure and trustworthy digital stamp of each heritage asset.

Traditional cryptocurrencies, such as BTC (Bitcoin), ETH (Ethereum), XRP (Ripple), and many others, are fungible. This means that, like regular money, you can always exchange n BTC for any other n BTC. In contrast, NFTs have the ability to be unique and exist as a single instance, making them suitable for representing various physical objects and assets in digital form.

For example, the tokenization of a building allows the representation of ownership rights in the digital world. By transferring the building's token on the blockchain network to

another person, the owner automatically transfers the ownership rights to that person and can immediately receive an equivalent amount in cryptocurrency upon executing a corresponding smart contract for the sale. This work proposes the adaptation of such a tokenization model to the conditions of an accounting system for cultural and historical values.

The main properties of ERC 721 standard tokens are [51]:

1. NFTs must represent a whole object from the real world that can be bought or sold.
2. Each NFT is unique and cannot be replaced by another. In the case of museum records, the token's metadata can contain an immutable record confirming its uniqueness. For example: "Painting, Mona Lisa, Leonardo da Vinci, 1503, Room 711, Denon Gallery, Louvre, Paris, France."
3. NFTs are created within the private account of the initial owner who creates them. For example, a museum, as the initial owner, has the right to transfer the tokenized rights to a painting to any other museum or private collector.
4. Given that blockchain ledgers are decentralized and immutable, all records of the creation and transfer of tokens can be verified at any time. Thus, when transferring ownership of a painting, the receiving museum can ascertain whether the first museum initially acquired the NFT token.
5. NFTs can be bought or sold through any blockchain infrastructure or custodial service among participants entitled to participate in this market of cultural values.

By exploiting the abovementioned features, NFTs are envisioned as a prominent solution for the future development of the cultural heritage management applications. Their unique properties and secure nature make them well-suited for accounting and tracking of the art objects across the world.

B. Blockchain as a Service Architecture

Blockchain as a Service (BaaS) offers managed blockchain platforms that simplify deployment, scalability, and

maintenance. This approach allows organizations to focus on developing applications and business logic while leaving the complex infrastructure management to the BaaS provider. For cultural heritage institutions, which often need more IT resources or expertise in blockchain, BaaS solutions are a practical and efficient choice [52].

Providers such as Microsoft Azure, IBM Blockchain, and Amazon Managed Blockchain offer services that support the setup, operation, and scaling of blockchain networks. These platforms address the specific needs of cultural heritage management, such as maintaining secure and immutable records, ensuring transparency, handling multiple stakeholders, and managing large volumes of data. BaaS solutions include encryption and access control, which protect sensitive artifact information and restrict blockchain access to authorized users only [53].

BaaS platforms are also highly scalable, capable of handling the growing data volumes and transaction rates associated with comprehensive cultural heritage systems. As new artifacts are added to the system and more stakeholders join the network, the platform scales to maintain consistent performance. This adaptability ensures that the system remains reliable as it grows.

One significant advantage of BaaS is its ability to integrate with Internet of Things (IoT) devices for environmental monitoring. Many BaaS platforms provide APIs and integration tools to connect IoT sensors directly to the blockchain [54]. These sensors can monitor conditions like temperature, humidity, and light exposure, recording data automatically on the blockchain. This helps track environmental conditions, detect anomalies, and preserve artifacts under optimal conditions.

Additionally, BaaS solutions offer user-friendly interfaces, such as dashboards and mobile apps, to simplify interactions with the blockchain. Curators, historians, and other stakeholders can access real-time updates, submit new data, and verify transactions through intuitive portals. This accessibility promotes engagement and ensures the blockchain system is practical for all users [55].

Therefore, BaaS platforms can provide cultural heritage institutions with a powerful, scalable, and user-friendly way to implement blockchain systems. These solutions may reduce the technical complexity, allowing institutions to focus on preserving and managing their artifacts efficiently and securely.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a blockchain-based framework for cultural heritage management to address the limitations of traditional methods in artifact authentication and provenance tracking. By leveraging blockchain's core features of immutability, decentralization, and transparency, along with advanced solutions for marking and scanning of art objects, the system provides a secure and scalable solution for preserving and managing cultural assets.

Integrating innovative technologies such as invisible markings, smart contracts, and NFTs enhances verifying authenticity, tracking provenance, and monitoring artifact conditions over time. Moreover, BaaS platforms simplify deployment and scalability, making blockchain technology

more accessible to cultural institutions that may lack technical expertise. A multi-blockchain architecture further optimizes the system by combining the strengths of various consensus algorithms to balance security, scalability, and efficiency.

By addressing the technical and practical challenges of implementing blockchain for cultural heritage, this work contributes a comprehensive methodology that strengthens artifact preservation, reduces fraud, and fosters stakeholder trust. This approach lays the foundation for a future where technology plays a pivotal role in safeguarding and enhancing the world's cultural heritage.

APPENDIX

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